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CORONAVIRUS (COVID-19) PANDEMIC AND CYBER-CRIMINAL ACTIVITIES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the activities of cyber-criminals over coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigeria. The paper is guided by the assumptions of Robert K. Merton's theory of Anomie developed in 1938. It adopted internet survey design. Qualitative method that does not require a sample size was adopted, and the study population consisted internet users. It also relied on convenience sampling technique among social media users. The primary data was collected through the use of interview schedule designed and circulated on social media platforms to get first hand information from the respondents, while secondary data was collected from the available information on the internet. Participations were invited from social media users who volunteered to participate in the online survey after seeking their consents. Data was collected from the study participants to the point of saturation. Content analysis and elaborate explanations were undertaken on the primary data. Findings among many others showed that social media users have been victims of cyber-crime, especially, those that are in dare need of government palliatives and the cybercriminals were still developing new methods to defraud members of the public in the post COVID-19 period. The study recommends that individuals on their part should ensure proper antimalware protection on their computer systems, they should be encouraged to avoid pirated software, never to share their Personal Identification Number (PIN), bank details, email access code to unknown persons, never disclose any confidential information to anybody as none of these networks were designed to be ultimately secure. Ignore any mail or attachment circulated on social media platforms requesting your banking details.

Keywords: Coronavirus (COVID-19), Pandemic, Cyber-crime and Cyber-criminals.

INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus, otherwise known as COVID-19 is a global pandemic (United Nations, 2020) and has taken the world by surprise. Coronavirus was discovered in 2019 in the city of Wuhan in China, hence the acronym COVID-19 (Boseley *et al.*, 2020). This global pandemic has negative effects on individuals, industries, economic activities, government establishments, and many others. It can spread through respiratory droplets when an infected person coughs or sneezes. Guirakhoo (2020) posited that COVID-19 itself, presents a significant global security risk to individuals and organizations across the world. Guirakhoo (2020) further added that cyber-criminal activities around this global pandemic have resulted in financial damage and had promoted dangerous guidance, ultimately putting additional strains on efforts to contain the virus. In other words, to prevent the spread of the disease, the government had put in place lockdown measures in different states. The Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) also advised that people should stay at home and avoid large gatherings (Owoseye, 2020).

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As always, cyber-criminals almost immediately began exploiting the situation for their own good by launching cyber-attacks that prey upon the public's fear and need for information. They use COVID-19 as the theme to lure victims into opening malicious attachments or links (Fraud Watch International, 2020). Cyber attacks are on the rise, endangering our sensitive information at an alarming rate (Haney and Lutters, 2017). Hewage (2020) also maintained that hackers have capitalized on this situation by sending out emails that purported to offer health advice from reputable organizations, such as governments and the World Health Organization (WHO) but that are really phishing attacks. It is hard to know how many attacks are being carried out or how many people are being affected. But new attacks are being reported nearly every day, and some cyber security companies are reporting large increases in enquiries since many people started working from home.

The coronavirus pandemic has brought with it extraordinary challenges for households, businesses, and communities across the nation. With restrictions to freedom of movement, combined with the fear, tension and stress related to COVID-19, cybercriminals have taken advantage of the COVID-19 panic, by targeting individuals and the negative impacts are on household incomes. As businesses are closed to help prevent transmission of COVID-19, financial concerns and job losses are some of the first human impacts of the virus. It is not a surprise that cyber criminals will use any issue to extort for their own gain, and COVID-19 is no exception – a lure to compromise victim's computers due to the confusion, urgency, misinformation and a personal connection for all.

Fidler (2020), Scheer and Satter (2020) and Central Bank of Nigeria (2020) were of the opinion that COVID-19 has dispersed people to their homes and many people have become more dependent on the internet as desperate measures to kill boredom and avoid being contracting COVID-19. It is this dependence that creates vulnerability among social media users.

A similar observation was made by Nicolas (2020) that cyber-criminals have taken advantage of the increasing amount of time that people spend online due to the spread of the COVID-19. Nicolas (2020) went further to add that the president of the European Commission, Ursula von der Leyen had observed on 24th March, 2020 that cyber-crime in the European Union (EU) has increased, due to the coronavirus outbreak. "They follow us online and exploit our concerns about the coronavirus. Our fear becomes their business opportunity," von der Leyen said in a video message (Nicolas, 2020).

As the fastest growing crime in the world at large (Interpol, 2013) with millions of people being affected every day, the financial losses accruing from cyber-crime is doubling every year (Tushabe and Baryamureeba, 2013). Yet, less than half of the cyber-crime instances are reported to the authorities. This means that the situation is worse than it seems to be. In Nigeria, Central Bank of Nigeria (2020) observed that cyber-criminals have taken advantage of the COVID-19 pandemic, defrauding citizens, by stealing sensitive information, or gain unauthorized access to computers or mobile devices using various techniques.

While most countries in the world are trying to deal with the COVID-19 pandemic, it seems the hackers are not on lockdown. Cyber criminals are trying to leverage the emergency by sending out "phishing" attacks that lure internet users to click on malicious links or files. This can allow the hackers to steal sensitive data or even take control of a user's device and use it to direct further attacks. Many people are searching online for information about COVID-19. But the pandemic has created what the World Health Organization (WHO) calls an "infodemic, in which people are bombarded with an overabundance of both accurate and inaccurate information that is circulating on the internet, making it hard to know what to trust (Hewage, 2020). The pandemic is also worsening the situation because more and more people are staying at home and using the internet to work and socialize. This means they may be using their personal computers more and working outside the normal security protections provided by their employers' internal computer systems. They are also working in stressful conditions that could leave them more likely to forget routine security procedures and fall victim to a phishing attack.

However, a scientific investigation has not been conducted regarding the activities of cyber-criminals over coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigeria. This exposes a significant shortage of information, which could serve as a policy framework against cyber-criminals in any disease outbreak. Therefore, this study has come to fill the gap by investigating the activities of cyber-criminals over the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigeria. This study is meaningful and necessary as the findings would create awareness, serve as background information for optimizing current security methods and generating advanced solutions from academic fields.

Against this background, the paper examined the different methods adopted by cyber-criminals to exploit people over coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic as well as the experiences of social media users toward cyber-criminal activities during coronavirus (COVID-19) with a view to proffering solutions to help stem the tide.

Conceptualizations

For the purpose of clarity, the following concepts are presented;

Coronavirus (COVID-19):

Coronaviruses are a large family of viruses that cause illness ranging from the common cold to more severe diseases such as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS). Coronavirus (COVID-19) is the name for the new strain of coronavirus that has not been previously identified in humans. Coronavirus (COVID-19) is a disease that started in Wuhan, China. It is caused by a member of the coronavirus family that has never been encountered before. Like other viruses, it has come from animals. Many of those initially infected either worked or frequently shopped in the Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market in the centre of the Chinese City (Boseley *et al.*, 2020).

Cyber-Crime:

Cybercrime is generally defined as a criminal offence involving a computer as the object of the crime (hacking, phishing, spamming), or as the tool used to commit a material component of the offence (child pornography, hate crimes, computer fraud). Criminals can also use computers for communication and data storage. A practical definition of a cyber crime is offered by Kshetri (2010). According to him, cyber-crime is defined as a criminal activity in which computers or computer networks are the principal means of committing an offence or violating laws, rules or regulations. Examples of cyber crime include denial of service attacks, cyber-theft, cyber trespass, cyber obscenity, critical infrastructure attacks, online fraud, online money laundering, Identity fraud, cyber terrorism, and cyber extortions. It is evident that organized criminal organizations use cyber crime extensively to collaborate and connect with their vast network which is spread across globe. The synergy between organized crime and the internet has thus increased the insecurity of the digital world.

However, the rise of the internet in Nigeria has come with an unintended consequence—global notoriety as a haven of cybercrime. Back in the 90s, fraud in the Nigerian society was popularly called 419 in reference to the criminal code that framed the criminal justice system in Nigeria. At the time, persons who were arrested in connection to that law were labeled ‘419’. Enforcement and a ponderous criminal justice system meant that the rampant practice of 419 was already a constant source of grief. Then along came the internet, shortly after which a number of tech-savvy cons successfully “exported” the 419 concept. While the popular 419 reference has since been extended to include cyber-criminals, in Nigeria the name “Yahoo-Yahoo” is the most familiar informal usage that is employed to speak of people who perpetrate scams online.

According to McGuire and Dorling (2013), cyber crime is an umbrella term used to describe two distinct, but closely related criminal activities: cyber-dependent and cyber-enabled crimes. In this paper, the use of ‘cyber crime’ refers to both forms of criminal activity, and we distinguish between them as outlined below;

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Cyber-dependent crimes are offences that can only be committed by using a computer, computer networks, or other form of ICT. These acts include the spread of viruses and other malicious software, hacking, and distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks, i.e. the flooding of internet servers to take down network infrastructure or websites. Cyber-dependent crimes are primarily acts directed against computers or network resources, although there may be secondary outcomes from the attacks, such as fraud.

Cyber-enabled crimes are traditional crimes that are increased in their scale or reach by the use of computers, computer networks or other ICT. Unlike cyber-dependent crimes, they can still be committed without the use of ICT. For the purposes of this review the following types of cyber-enabled crimes are included: fraud (including mass-marketing frauds, ‘phishing’ e-mails and other scams; online banking and e-commerce frauds); theft (including theft of personal information and identification-related data); and o sexual offending against children (including grooming, and the possession, creation and/or distribution of sexual imagery).

Central Bank of Nigeria (2020) observed that the cyber-criminals send out emails claiming to be from health organizations such as the Nigerian Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) or the World Health Organizations (WHO). The email may contain a link which, if clicked, steals login credentials or other confidential information from the victim’s computer or mobile device. The cyber-criminals also send messages via social media or emails asking people to click on links to register in order to get their COVID-19 relief packages from the government or other organizations. They simply just use this to get confidential information from unwary victims. Relief package scams also come in the form of phone calls asking people to provide their banking details to receive relief packages. The criminals also ask unsuspecting customers to get the bank mobile apps, which they use to steal information from their victims’ mobile phones, among other things. They have also produced COVID-19 maps which steal information in the background.

CYBER-CRIMINAL ACTIVITIES

This refers to crimes committed in the cyberspace through modern technological advancements. According to Central Bank Nigeria (2020), the following are cyber-criminal activities are prominent in the COVID-19 pandemic;

Phishing:

Cyber-criminals send out emails claiming to be from health organizations such as the Nigerian Center for Disease Control (NCDC) or the World Health Organization (WHO). The email may contain a link which, if clicked, steals login credentials or other confidential information from the victim’s computer or mobile device (Central Bank Nigeria, 2020). Guirakhoo (2020) further added that phishing is one of, if not the single most common attack techniques. Reports of email phishing campaigns using COVID-19-related lures surfaced almost immediately after confirmed infections began increasing in January 2020. Health organizations such as the WHO and US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) have been prime targets for impersonation due to their perceived authority: Attackers have been observed tempting victims with URLs or document downloads using promises of important safety documentation or infection maps. Another phishing scam, as detailed by Sophos, impersonated an official email correspondence from the WHO. The email contained a link to purported document on preventing the spread of the virus, but redirected victims to a malicious domain which attempted to harvest credentials. The email contained several grammatical and format errors, which can be used by attackers to narrow down their victims and bypass spam filters. These campaigns are often targeted towards geographies which have significant numbers of COVID-19 infections. In late January 2020, a phishing campaign targeted individuals in Japan with emails claiming to be from disability welfare service providers and public health centers. The emails used lures of documents containing information on alerts of new COVID-19 infections as well as preventative measures against the virus.

However, when accessed, the documents attempted to download and install Emotet, an information stealing malware. Similarly, individuals in Italy, which has the highest number of confirmed infections of COVID-19 outside of China, were targeted by a phishing campaign in March 2020 which impersonated WHO officials and attempted to distribute the Trickbot trojan.

Relief Packages:

Cyber-criminals have also been sending messages via social media or emails asking people to click on links to register in order to get their COVID-19 relief packages from the Government or other organizations. They simply use this to get confidential information from unwary victims. Relief package scams also come in the form of phone calls asking people to provide their banking details to receive relief packages (Central Bank Nigeria, 2020)..

Impersonation:

Cyber-criminals place calls to individuals claiming to be staff of their banks and asking them to get mobile apps that would help them get through this pandemic period. Such mobile apps are however used to steal information from the victims' mobile phones among other things. Criminals have also produced COVID-19 maps, which steal information in the background (Central Bank Nigeria, 2020). Guirakhoo (2020) also observed that COVID-19-related misinformation has primarily been spread via social media and private messaging platforms. Misinformation does not always have the same tangible financial impact as other types of cybercriminal activity, but it can still be used to cause panic, incite racism and xenophobia, promote harmful at-home cures, and result in shortages of supplies and critical medical equipment. The WHO has labeled this proliferation of information – both legitimate and not – as an “infodemic”, and have assembled a dedicated team to manage the spread of potentially harmful misinformation. Social media platforms themselves have also taken a proactive approach to help prevent the spread of false information related to COVID-19 by flagging posts which may be illegitimate and hiring third-party organizations to fact-check posts. When searching COVID-19-related terms on platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and even Instagram, users are prompted to obtain information from official sources. This can even help streamline the dissemination of legitimate information by providing centralized results.

However, Guirakhoo (2020) cautioned that while some cyber-criminals may appear sympathetic with coronavirus victims, many continue to try to take advantage of the situation.

Fraud:

Fraud is a criminal activity in which someone pretends to be somebody and retrieve vital information about someone. The concept is simple; someone gains access to your personal information and uses it for his own benefit. This could range from a black-hat hacker stealing online banking account login and password to getting access to ATMs and using such stolen information; people can make themselves a lot of money. In Nigeria people design web links forms requesting users to fill in their basic information including, unique details like pin numbers and use the information obtained to commit crimes. For example, on May 9, 2013 an international gang of cyber thieves stole more than \$45 million from thousands of ATMs in a carefully coordinated attack conducted in a matter of hours (USA Today, 2013). Luna *et al.* (2016) have carried out a systematic review on cyber threats to health information systems and discovered that the most prevalent cyber-criminal activity in healthcare is identity theft through data breach.

Malware:

Malware refers to viruses, Trojans, worms and other software that gets onto your computer without you being aware it is there. Once downloaded, these malwares can wreak havoc on an organization or national information system by infecting the computer system and destroying valuable information.

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The Trojan horse is also a technique for creating an automated form of computer abuse called the salami attack, which works on financial data. This technique causes small amounts of assets to be removed from a larger pool. The stolen assets are removed one slice at a time.

Murphy and Cook (2020) were of the opinion that the rise of coronavirus-related cyber-attacks began in January, 2020 before escalating in February, 2020. The Covid-19 outbreak represents a ready-made pretext for cyber criminals. This pretext is what opens hospitals or local government departments up to phishing or social engineering attacks. Once the malware is on the system, it could locate and encrypt, or temporarily hold, crucial files that cause outages impacting clinical staff. A staff member who clicks on a link in an urgent-looking email from what appears to be the World Health Organization could allow hackers to infiltrate entire networks of hospitals and NHS trusts, stealing crucial files and holding hospitals, whose priority is keeping patients alive, to ransom.

Spam:

Spam is the use of electronic messaging systems to send unsolicited bulk messages indiscriminately. While the most widely recognized form of spam is e-mail spam, the term is applied to similar abuses in other media: instant messaging spam, Usenet newsgroup spam, web search engine spam, spam in blogs, wiki spam, online classified ads spam, mobile phone messaging spam, internet forum spam, junk fax transmissions, social networking spam, television advertising and file sharing network spam. Some of these address harvesting approaches rely on users not reading the fine print of agreements, resulting in them agreeing to send messages indiscriminately to their contacts. This is a common approach in social networking spam such as that generated by the social networking site (Saul, 2007). Spamming remains economically viable because advertisers have no operating costs beyond the management of their mailing lists, and it is difficult to hold senders accountable for their mass mailings. Because the barrier to entry is so low, spammers are numerous, and the volume of unsolicited mail has become very high. A person who creates electronic spam is called a spammer (Gyongyi, 2005).

Mandavia (2020) posited that cyber criminals are exploiting interest in COVID-19 to spread malicious activity through several spam campaigns relating to the outbreak. Mandavia (2020) further added that as the virus spreads across the globe, people are searching online for the latest information and updates on how it might affect them, and what they can do to protect themselves and their families. Cyber criminals are quick to take advantage of these concerns for their own gain. Many of these domains will probably be used for phishing attempts. There have been over 4,000 coronavirus-related domains registered globally since January. Out of these websites, 3% were found to be malicious and an additional 5% are suspicious, it added. Coronavirus-related domains are 50% more likely to be malicious than other domains registered at the same period.

Hacking:

Timberg and Romm (2020) observed that Chinese hackers have used fake documents about the coronavirus to deliver malicious software and steal sensitive user information. As the novel coronavirus has moved across the world, cyber-criminals and spies have taken advantage of the growing demand for information by loading malicious software into tracking maps, government reports and health fact sheets in numerous languages. New websites with variations on “coronavirus” in their Internet addresses also have exploded, with many of them masking online scams. As the novel coronavirus has moved across the world, cyber-criminals and spies have taken advantage of the growing demand for information by loading malicious software into tracking maps, government reports and health fact sheets in numerous languages. New websites with variations on “coronavirus” in their internet addresses also have exploded, with many of them masking online scams.

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Password Sniffing:

Password sniffers are able to monitor all traffic on areas of a network. Hackers have installed them on networks used by systems that they especially want to penetrate, like telephone systems and network providers. Password sniffers are programs that simply collect the first 128 or more bytes of each network connection on the network that's being monitored. When a user types in a user name and a password as required when using certain common internet services like FTP (which is used to transfer files from one machine to another) or Telnet (which lets the user log in remotely to another machine) the sniffer collects that information. Additional programs sift through the collected information, pull out the important pieces (e.g., the user names and passwords) and cover up the existence of the sniffers in an automated way. Best example, in 1994 as many as 100,000 sites were affected by sniffer attacks (David, 1995).

International Bank Transfer Fraud:

As you are aware the internet stretches to every corner of the world and on the internet, you have people who find opportunity in the form of Fraud (Lying and Cheating); the many good online businesses using the internet to conduct their international business using any and all means available to them. These criminals - commonly called Scammers - use forged documents from banks, forged/fake cheques, fake identity and passports, and of course use the internet sites posing as potential buyers to receive Performa Invoices (which they get your account information from and then steal your company identity, even possibly your identity to use in new crimes) from suppliers, etc. Most of these people are professionals at it, and make thousands of dollars a year preying on the good trust of people who believe they are a real buyer or a person in need.

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) recently warned about suspicious email messages attempting to take advantage of the Covid-19 emergency by stealing money and sensitive information from the public. However, according to new reports, hacking attempts against WHO's own computer systems and its partners have increased during the coronavirus outbreak. Although the aim of these attacks is unclear, one might presume a multitude of motives for attacking prominent health organizations during this pandemic. For example, cyber-criminals could be looking for information about cures, tests or vaccines relating to the coronavirus to sell in the black market, encrypt sensitive data and hold it for ransom, or simply disrupt the operability of the institution.

LAWS AGAINST CYBERCRIME IN NIGERIA

The Cybercrime Act is made up of 59 Sections, 8 Parts; and 2 Schedules. 1st Schedule lists the Cybercrime Advisory Council, 2nd Schedule lists businesses to be levied for the purpose of the Cyber security Fund under Section 44(2) (a) GSM service providers and all telecom companies; Internet service providers, banks and other financial institutions, insurance companies and Nigerian Stock Exchange (Cybercrime Act, 2015).

Below is a high-level overview of certain interesting provisions in the recently passed Cyber-crime Act, 2015 as it relates to the subject matter.

- I. Gives the President the power to designate certain computer systems, networks and information infrastructure vital to the national security of Nigeria or the economic and social well-being of its citizens, as constituting Critical National Information Infrastructure and to implement procedures, guidelines and conduct audits in furtherance of that. Examples of systems which could be designated as such include transport, communication, banking etc.
- II. Prescribes the death penalty for an offence committed against a system or network that has been designated critical national infrastructure of Nigeria that results in the death of an individual or/and loss in financial transaction.

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- III. Hackers, if found guilty of unlawfully accessing a computer system or network, are liable to a fine of up to N10 million or a term of imprisonment of 5 years (depending on the purpose of the hack). The same punishment is also meted out to Internet fraudsters who perpetuate their acts either by sending electronic messages or accessing and using data stored on computer systems.
- IV. Makes provision for identity theft, with the punishment of imprisonment for a term of not less than 3 years or a fine of not less than N7 million or to both fine and imprisonment.
- V. Specifically creates child pornography offences, with punishments of imprisonment for a term of 10 years or a fine of not less than N20 million or to both fine and imprisonment, depending on the nature of the offence and the act carried out by the accused persons. Offences include, amongst others: producing, procuring, distributing, and possession of child pornography.
- VI. Outlaws Cyber-stalking and Cyber-bullying and prescribes punishment ranging from a fine of not less than N2 million or imprisonment for a term of not less than 1 year or to both fine and imprisonment, up to a term of not less than 10 years or a fine of not less than N25 million or to both fine and imprisonment; depending on the severity of the offence.
- VII. Prohibits cyber-squatting, which is registering or using an Internet domain name with bad faith intent to profit from the goodwill of a trademark belonging to someone else or to profit by selling to its rightful owner. Individuals who engage in this are liable on conviction to imprisonment for a term of not less than 2 years or a fine of not less than N5 million or to both fine and imprisonment.
- VIII. Forbids the distribution of racist and xenophobic material to the public through a computer system or network (e.g. Facebook and Twitter), it also prohibits the use of threats of violence and insulting statements to persons based on race, religion, colour, descent or national or ethnic origin. Persons found guilty of this are liable on conviction to imprisonment for a term of not less than 5 years or to a fine of not less than N10million or to both fine and imprisonment.
- IX. Mandates that service providers shall keep all traffic data and subscriber information having due regard to the individual's constitutional Right to privacy and shall take appropriate measures to safeguard the confidentiality of the data retained, processed or retrieved.
- X. Allows for the interception of electronic communication by way of a court order by a Judge, where there are reasonable grounds to suspect that the content of any electronic communication is reasonably required for the purposes of a criminal investigation or proceedings.

Theory and Method

The study was guided by the assumptions of Robert K. Merton's theory of Anomie developed in 1938. Merton used anomie theory to apply specifically to deviant behaviour in various societies. In the contemporary society, success is probably rated a lot higher than virtue. His theory proposes that those individuals, who are underprivileged, may end up as taking honest and socially acceptable path to meet financial success and yet not end up as successful, as those who are not in the same position. This would lead them to question why they would take the honest path when they could be more successful through deviant behaviour. Merton (1938) opines that gap between approved goals and the means creates strain.

In contemporary society, success is primarily measured in terms of material achievements and social standing. In a mixed shape of economy such as Nigeria, individuals have to choose their own path and work hard to earn a living. This leads to competitive nature of careers and employment. Cyber criminals are from a very diverse background. Those who are in higher schools or colleges are most likely to fit into this theory. They may see how they put a lot of hard work into their studies and development of skills and yet realize that it is unlikely that they could achieve the financial success. As a result they may see crime as a means to achieve enormous financial success. Any individual would see computer crime as a way and means to make large sums of illegitimate money.

It is not surprising that the undue emphasis placed on the societal goal of achieving monetary success and material acquisition certainly produced and reproduced a multiplicity of offences. In this regard, criminal offences are reinvigorating, hence, resulting to the rising rate of cyber-crime in our society. This is supported by R. V. Clark's situational crime prevention proposition which presupposes that for crimes to occur there must be a law, an environment, a safe target, a requisite rational activity, and a willing offender (Clark and Eck, 2003; Brown, 2016).

The study adopted internet survey design. The choice of internet survey design was because of its considerable cost savings when compared to other survey methods. Qualitative method that does not require a sample size was adopted. The study also relied on convenience sampling technique. The primary data was collected through the use of unstructured interview guide circulated online to get first hand information from the respondents while secondary data was collected from the available information on the internet. The researcher invited participations from social media users who volunteered to participate in the online survey after sorting their consents. Data was collected from the study participants to the point of saturation (a point where respondents were no longer provided new information regarding the research objectives). The likely questions were open ended regarding the study objectives. The reason was to give room for the study participants to express their opinions. Content analysis and elaborate explanations were undertaken on the primary data.

DATA, FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The fieldwork yielded useful information on the activities of cyber-criminals over COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria;

QUESTION 1: What are the Different Methods Adopted by Cyber Criminals to Exploit People amid Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic?

Findings show that the different methods adopted by cyber-criminals to exploit people over coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic include; phishing scams, malicious websites, malicious Apps, malware, hacking, spam, misinformation, fraudulent products and hacking. Phishing scam is commonly found in the cyber-space more than others. Phishing scams are attempts by scammers to trick you into giving out your personal information such as your bank account numbers, passwords and ATM PIN code. There have been numerous emails going around containing links or attachments supposedly providing information about the Coronavirus, when in fact, they aim to infect PCs or mobile devices with malware. A variety of phishing campaigns are taking advantage of the heightened focus on COVID-19 to distribute malware, steal credentials, and scam users out of money. The attacks use common phishing tactics that are seen regularly, however a growing number of campaigns are using the coronavirus as a lure to try to trick distracted users capitalize on the fear and uncertainty of their intended victims. Phishing attacks have promised financial relief due to the coronavirus pandemic – but in reality swiped victims' credentials, payment card data and more.

Cyber-criminals have been sending phishing emails that promise exclusive information in the form of attachments and links to protection gear at highly discounted prices. While working from home might seem like a respite from office life, staying indoors means we will all be spending more time online reading news, shopping, and going through emails. Whether it is through laptop or Android phone, more time spent online means more exposure to fraud, phishing, and malware. They all attempt to exploit our curiosity and basic necessities, such as the need to buy medical or personal hygiene equipment or other goods. Fraudsters are impersonating the federal government of Nigeria and institutions affiliated with or linked to the Nigeria Center for Disease Control (NCDC) and the World Health Organization (WHO) for financial relief in the form of palliatives. Another series of messages that allegedly offer new updates in the Coronavirus outbreak is the use logos from the World Health Organization to appear legitimate.

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They entice readers with grants and donations sponsored by the World Bank Group, United Nations, World Health Organization, Asian Development Bank, World Trade Organization, International Monetary Fund, European Central Bank, Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, International Finance Corporation and many more. Individuals are being sent a huge variety of emails which impersonate authorities, such as the World Health Organization (WHO), in an effort to persuade victims to download software or donate to bogus causes. Cyber-criminals are also attempting to capitalize on government support packages by imitating public institutions.

The figures below depict some of the activities of cyber-criminals in the cyber space;

Figure 1: an example of scam circulated on social media.

Figure 2: Dangerous attachment on COVID-19 payment

Figure 3: One of the scam emails that impersonates the WHO

Umoh Esara shared information on social media on the 16th April, 2020 thus;

This number 07025208428 is calling around, proclaiming he's calling from Zenith Bank Headquarters. He will tell you your name; Date of Birth and your BVN. He will then ask you to supply your account number that they want to register you for Federal Government N25000 grant. This information is a scam and nobody should supply his/her account number. Please share to save others too.

Also, Stephen Robert also shared information on social media on 16th April, 2020 thus;

Security Alert! A few minutes ago, somebody called me supposedly from Zenith Marina Lagos, requesting my Zenith Bank card number. He told me that they wish to credit my account with N25, 500, being my own share of the COVID-19 relief package from the Federal Government. He dictated my BVN and my date of birth and asked me to confirm both details, which to my surprise, he got correctly. He advises me not to get off the phone since I have only 10 minutes to give him the information he requested from me. Nonetheless, I switched off. He called me back and was upset that I went off my phone. I told him that I went to look for my ATM Card. He asked me if I have the number ready, I told him that I am still looking for it. He now started advising me about the need to strictly adhere to the Federal Government fight against corruption. He talked about the need to be careful in all my dealings, since unscrupulous people are duping people of their hard earned money. I listened patiently. He then asked me if I have the card number ready, I reminded him that they from the bank have asked us not to release our bank information. He said yes, but told me that his request is different because they need to credit my account based on Federal Government directive. I told him to please permit me to call my accounts officer from Zenith bank. When he went on to argue, I switched off and called my account officer who told me that the man is a fraudster. He expressed frustration on what is currently going on. He begged me to share this story so that others will be informed. Please people, be careful and ensure that these fraudsters do not convince you to give out your card information”.

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It is evident in the study that a lot of websites and emails have been appearing containing false information regarding the COVID-19 pandemic, meant to frighten the public or get people to take actions they would not otherwise taken, pretending to be an update official organizations, such as the WHO, NCDC, etc. on the coronavirus outbreak containing a file which ends up in installing a malware allowing the sender to steal the sensitive data from mobiles and computers. Some of these scams are in the form of donation requests for fake charities and several malicious apps have also been uploaded to app stores (Google Play, Apple Store), mostly disguised as Coronavirus related content. The World Health Organization (WHO) recently warned about suspicious email messages that are attempted to take advantage of COVID-19 emergency for stealing money and sensitive information from the public.

This study is in line with Rohrlich (2020) who posited that as the coronavirus pandemic continues to spread across the world, authorities have seen a simultaneous outbreak of opportunistic cyber scams. Cyber-criminals will find ways to take advantage of people's fears and uncertainties in the wake of major disasters and emergencies. Rohrlich (2020) went further to add that cyber actors may send emails with malicious attachments or links to fraudulent websites to trick victims into revealing sensitive information or donating to fraudulent charities or causes. Rohrlich (2020) advised the public to exercise caution in handling any email with a Covid-19-related subject line, attachment, or hyperlink, and be wary of social media pleas, texts, or calls related to Covid-19.

QUESTION 2: What Has Been the Experience of Social Media Users over Cyber-Criminal Activities Regarding Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic?

Findings show that the promises made by various governments to help citizens is misused by the hackers by sending fraudulent text messages in the name of linking their bank accounts with the government which ultimately lands in compromising with bank accounts of unsuspecting victims and misappropriation of these funds. The criminals are aiming at personal information in one or another way as without sensitive personal data, online crime cannot be done. In order to extract the information, the hackers are sending communication wrapping spyware in the name of coronavirus, as recently an email feigning it to be an official notification about the closure of schools, colleges and cinema halls in Nigeria has been sent to various people, following which their devices were compromised at the very instant they clicked on the attachment.

In the words of respondents, when asked about their experiences concerning cyber-criminal activities during COVID-19 outbreak:

Emmanuel Jonathan (male) in an interview on social media on 21st April, 2020 said;

You would agree with me that more people than ever are working from home or elsewhere in isolation because of the restriction of movement order by the government in a way to prevent the novel coronavirus outbreak. I spent much of my time on the internet than anywhere else. I am aware of the sharp increase in cyber-attacks on people. Let me say that I am a victim of cyber-crime. I had this encounter on the 7th April, 2020 when false information was circulated on the social media that the federal government of Nigeria was going to provide financial relief of N8, 500 weekly for Nigerians who have existing bank account and Bank Verification Number (BVN). Unfortunately for me, my friend forwarded an attachment to my WhatsApp page requiring my personal information including my bank details before I could access the said financial relief. I quickly supplied the needed information after which I waited for weeks without anything dropping in my account from the Federal Government. It was at that point that I discovered that I submitted my personal information to scammers. I regretted my actions that day. The message goes thus "NIGERIAN GOVERNMENT SWINGS INTO ACTION! All Nigerian citizens are entitled to N8500 per week to stay at home in a bid to control the spread of COVID 19. The government grant is available to everyone starting From Monday 23 March 2020. CLICK TO APPLY ==> https://bit.ly/FG_Covid-19_Grants"

Another respondent Emem John Etuk (female) in an interview on social media on 20th April, 2020 said that;

I do not doubt that scammers have been sending fake emails and text messages claiming to be from the Federal Government of Nigeria, World Health Organization (WHO) and even individuals like Aliko Dangote, former President Olusegun Obasanjo, President Donald Trump, etc. The yahoo boys are making illegitimate financial gains from COVID-19 pandemic. Although, I have never been a victim of cyber-crime, a lot of my friends and colleagues in my place of work are victims. They disclosed their personal information to unknown persons in disguise by filling financial relief disbursement form believing to be from the Federal Government of Nigeria to cushion the effect of coronavirus. Yet, their bank accounts have been drained to zero. This trend has been in the increase due to hunger in the land and people are looking for palliatives especially from the government and NGOs to sustain their livelihoods. It is as a result that people are in dire need of financial relief that lured so many of them to cyber-criminals, especially, those who have access to the internet.

Another respondent Kinsley Edem (male) in an interview on social media on 21th April, 2020 said that;

If there is one thing certain during a pandemic, it is that hackers will use it for their own gain. While most countries of the world are trying to deal with the COVID-19 pandemic, cyber-criminals used this opportunity to scam people. They do this by sending out phishing emails that lure internet users to click on malicious links or files. This allowed the hackers to steal sensitive data or information and even take control of a user's device and use it to direct further attacks. These emails and documents look authentic and provide relevant information. But opening the file installs a malicious piece of code on the victim's computer that runs every time they open their word processing application (for example Microsoft Word). The COVID-19 is also worsening the situation because more and more people are staying at home and using the internet to work and socialize. This means they may be using their personal computers more and working outside the normal security protections provided by their employers' internal computer systems. They are also working in stressful conditions that could leave them more likely to forget routine security procedures and fall victim to a phishing attack. Luckily, there are some simple things you can do to spot and deal with phishing attacks. Most simply, you can check for obvious signs of fake or unofficial emails such as poor spelling, grammar and punctuation, as most of these emails are generated from outside the country they are sent to. But also be wary if the email tries to create a sense of urgency, that you must click its link now. And if the content seems too good to be true then it probably is. You should also bear in mind that cyber criminals use every opportunity available to exploit weaknesses in cyber security. And a frantic search for health advice is such an opportunity. So you should always make sure that you look for information about COVID-19 on trusted sources such as the WHO. I know people who are victims of cyber-criminals following the COVID-19 lockdown and my candid advice is that online users should confirm the source of information before any meaningful action is being taken.

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From these narratives, the restriction of movement regulations in different states in Nigeria has given room for cyber-criminals to take advantage of the fear and uncertainty surrounding the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. Cyber-criminals are opportunistic and will look to exploit people's fears, and this has undoubtedly been the case with the coronavirus outbreak. It was found in the study that Government lockdown as a result of coronavirus (COVID-19) situation has encouraged cyber-criminals to exploit people online and their concern about corona virus and related activities. The nationwide lockdown has forced millions of people to stay at home and in the course of keeping themselves occupied to avoid boredom, spent more time on the internet. Malicious cyber actors were using the high appetite for Covid-19 related information as an opportunity to deliver malware and ransomware and to steal user credentials. They create a malicious Android app purporting to provide real-time updates about Covid-19 outbreaks but instead installing ransomware that locked down a user's phone until they agreed to pay to regain access. It is evident in the study that a good number of social media users have become victims of cyber-criminals basically on the grounds that people believe that they can access palliatives from government by sending authentic personal information as a proof for identification.

CONCLUSION

The paper examined the activities of cyber-criminals over coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigeria. From the foregoing, it could be concluded that the issue of cyber-criminal activities in Nigeria regarding coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak requires urgent attention. COVID-19 is one of the most severe challenges humanity has ever faced, presenting a significant risk to individuals and organizations across the world. The activity of opportunistic cyber-criminals can make this challenge even more difficult to overcome by destabilizing critical infrastructure and creating panic. Since the Coronavirus (COVID-19) shows no signs of disappearing anytime soon, it is safe to assume that cyber-criminals will continue to exploit the situation and create more attacks, using the methods mentioned above and even devising new ways as well. It is important for social media users to be vigilant as possible while using the internet. It is recommended that;

Social media users must be familiar with the different techniques and methods used by the cyber-criminals. This coordinating role has to be played by the government or its agencies, stakeholders such as banks, e-commerce companies, media and websites.

Social media users must be conscious of every electronic information within their disposal regarding COVID-19 to know if it is from an unrecognized address or contains grammar and spelling mistakes. Avoid opening links or attachments from unknown sources. It is possible to hover the mouse cursor over hyperlinks to see where they actually lead. Avoid emails or advertisements that urge you to "act now". This sense of urgency is meant to enhance the already induced panic of the situation, to pressure people into making irrational decisions.

Individuals on their part should ensure proper antimalware protection on their computer systems and mobile phones, they should be encouraged to avoid pirated software, never to disclose any confidential information or share their Personal Identification Number (PIN), Ignore any e-mail requiring any financial information like bank details and email access code to unknown persons.

All ill intended spam must be reported immediately to the appropriate authorities. Telecommunication Regulatory Agencies should enhance security on internet service providers' server in other to detect and trace cyber-criminals.

There is need for the government to engage cyber security experts in the fight while aiding the existing law enforcement agencies, intelligence agencies and security agencies to understand both the nature of technology and the individuals involved in cybercrime. In order to effectively curb the rate of cyber-crime, the government needs to enact enforceable laws to punish offenders.

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